

Workshop Summary

Workshop Title: [Open Data in Geochemistry Part 2: Managing, Publishing, and Archiving Imagery Generated by Geochemical and Cosmochemical Sample Analysis](#)

Workshop Description: The production and use of 2D and 3D imagery in geochemistry and cosmochemistry is becoming pervasive due to advancements in analytical instrumentation that can quantitatively measure elemental concentrations and isotopic compositions of samples in-situ across large areas or at increasingly higher spatial resolution with methods such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), electron microprobe (EMP), secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS). Increasingly, along with precise point analysis, these techniques now produce quantitative maps, which need to be connected with the geochemical and textural data of the mineral phases in a sample. This combination of spatial imaging and microanalysis of features such as chondrules, melt inclusions, and the matrix results in a complete contextual understanding of a sample.

Infrastructure, software tools, and Best Practices for managing, publishing, and archiving geochemical and cosmochemical imagery are sparse. Current geochemistry data repositories are generally not equipped to host large volumes of images and provide users with tools to work with these images. This workshop is intended to start a dialog among geochemists /cosmochemists, data repositories, software tool developers, instrument manufacturers, and publishers with the goal to identify and articulate requirements, including archiving infrastructure, data standards and Best Practices, and tools that support the management and sharing of imagery in geochemistry and cosmochemistry. The workshop will feature invited presentations showcasing the use of imagery in geochemistry; demonstrations of existing and emerging software tools for managing and analyzing imagery; a panel discussion of experts regarding Best Practices; and group discussions to identify community needs.

Summary of workshop themes and talks:

The workshop served as a platform to discuss the wide range of microanalysis images being generated across several types of instrumentation (SEM, TEM, various LA-MS systems, optical micro, etc). The general frame of reference was set out by J. Einsle (Glasgow)

One core theme that emerged that was the question of how to get all these different types of images to work together. The presentations by R. Taylor (Zeiss), G. Robson (iif) and P. Haenecour (UA) all presented various tools for performing correlative microscopy on a variety of image types. These all rely on the data living at least in some kind of data archive, which at the moment there seems to be very few public image repositories for these types of data.

Related to this was also the discussion of the volume of data that is generated in high-resolution imaging experiments pushes into the lower edge of big data very quickly, whereas more traditional geochemical data sets are still very much small data (at least in terms of size per experiment). This resulted in some discussion of need for repositories willing to host image data and meet FAIR criteria. We did hear from O. Plümper (Utrecht) on how the Excite network has been sharing project data via the EPOS data portal. We also heard from K. Lehnert who provided details on what has previously been achieved with EarthChem as well as some links to what has been achieved in other communities (notably biology and medical imaging) in this space.

Finally, the lack of image standards was discussed as well. This takes the form of both of imaging types where spectral or diffraction data are acquired these files are usually stored in proprietary formats (or custom ones if from a synchrotron). J. Einsle discusses that there were some tools for converting to open formats, but that this is still a piecemeal operation.

Actions:

1. Create a community to share slides from workshop, relevant methods etc.
 - a. Owner: K. Lehnert
 - b. Update: decided to add this to the Earth Chem as a Community
2. Share slides with workshop attendees.
 - a. Owner: J. Einsle
 - b. Action: could all speakers send their slides to Josh for archiving and eventual upload on the community site once it is created
3. Editorial article on need for community archives for geochemical imaging data (Eos or Science)
 - a. Owner: J. Einsle
 - b. Updates: K. Lehnert to follow up with Science editor on if this would fit there
4. AGU abstract on making microscopic imagery accessible and reusable.
 - a. Owner: J. Einsle
 - b. Question / Action for all: do all workshop participants want to be co-authors?
 - c. Updates: currently drafting, will be a modification of the workshop abstract.
5. Develop further workshops/ webinars where other communities and tools for working with and archiving data can be presented for the community to develop a consensus around what and how to proceed.
6. Also host some further workshops on technical topics resulting in a recommended image standards – both in terms of format but also in terms of metadata.